

An in-house made autosampler for capillary electrophoresis

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HIGHLIGHTS

- A compact (9x9x26 cm w. d. h.) auto-sampler for capillary electrophoresis is presented.
- The sequence of actions for using the device is entirely automatized.
- Direct hydrodynamic injection from the sample allows use of a few nanoliters of it.
- The proposed assembly showed performances comparable with commercial devices.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Researchers are developing customized capillary electrophoresis (CE) instruments due to their affordability, and versatility. CE's simplicity, compared to chromatography-based methods, allows for low-cost designs using commercially available components. Injection methods, however, necessitate particular attention because of the high reproducibility required for quantitative determinations. Traditional manual hydrodynamic and electrokinetic injections involve one or more actions by the user thus increasing the number of potential sources of error. Automation efforts, such as using syringe pumps and pressure controllers, have improved injection precision, achieving results comparable to commercial systems. Despite progress, many methods still require manual sample loading and flushing, highlighting the need for further innovation in CE automation.

Results: A compact (26 x 9 x 9 cm) autosampler for a capillary electrophoresis (CE) system was designed, optimized and tested. The entire system was built in-house using the Open-Source Hardware (OSH) approach. It facilitates the fully automated analysis of a sequence of samples reducing the number of manual operations required by the user. The device allows hydrodynamic injection by pressure from six vials, as well as automatic rinsing of the capillary, and was coupled to a purpose made CE instrument with contactless conductivity detector (C4D). A precision better than 2.4 % was obtained for peak areas in the measurement of inorganic cations. The in-house made autosampler was used for analysing mineral water and the accuracies regarding the determination of the analytes were comparable to those observed for already published approaches.

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Significance: The significance of this research lies in running automated analysis sequences with an in-house-built injector that performs on par with commercial systems. The open-source hardware approach simplifies upgrades, supports the integration of new features, and allows the creation of complementary devices, making the system highly adaptable to evolving challenges and requirements.

1. Introduction

Several research groups have been exploring the potential of assembling customised capillary electrophoresis (CE) instruments for a variety of reasons: i. the ability to perform analyses in situ [1]; ii. the affordability of instrumentation [2]; iii. the democratisation of science [3]. In fact, the main components of the instruments, including the high voltage power supply supplies, detectors, data acquisition and management systems, are commercially available and their in-house assembly allowed the construction of affordable and portable instruments. In addition, this trend has recently been encouraged by the availability of tools and components for the in-house building of laboratory equipment, following the open source movement [4,5], and various examples of capillary electrophoresis instruments have already been proposed [2, 6–8]. Although the versatility of CE can easily be seen in its ability to study different species, ranging from small ions to macromolecules [9], from an instrumental point of view, the flexibility of this analytical method is mainly due to the inherent simplicity of the device. In particular, if compared to high-pressure liquid chromatography, CE does not require pressures in the hundreds of bar for moving the components of the sample through the chromatographic column, but the separation is carried out by applying a high voltage for the separation of the ions in the capillary. Thus, in CE the driving force of the separation medium is generated electronically, not mechanically, facilitating the building of low-cost and compact devices. Studies regarding the detection, aimed at improving sensitivity and specificity, represent the main area of investigation. Detectors for capillary electrophoresis include fluorimeters [10], mass spectrometers [11], conductometers [12], amperometers [13] and absorbance photometers [14]. Although the ability to unambiguously detect small amounts of the analyte is the main objective in the development of customised instruments and novel analytical methods, injection is also a critical aspect.

In the past, many approaches were based on individual manual hydrodynamic injection using the siphon effect, or on electrokinetic injection. These two methods were chosen for their inherent simplicity, but some critical weaknesses are known. For manual siphoning injection, the steps to perform the injection, such as lifting, vial exchange and capillary immersion, are difficult to control precisely resulting in an inaccuracy of injection within 5–10 % [15]. Electrokinetic injection imparts low accuracy for quantification of samples with different conductivities, mostly limiting its use for the quantification of samples with similar conductivity [15]. Due to these shortcomings, efforts have been made to automate hydrodynamic injection by applying pressure, rather than using siphoning. Worth mentioning is the strategy proposed by Koenka et al. [16]. In the report, the authors proposed the use of off-the-shelf miniature components, including syringe pumps, valves and pressure controllers on a breadboard for managing fluid movement. The authors demonstrated a performance comparable to commercial CE systems. Some improvements were subsequently proposed by the same [2,8,17] and other research groups [1,18,19]. Although these reports demonstrated refinements, they are based on individual injections and consequently require manual intervention of the operator to load each sample and possibly also for flushing of the capillary.

To overcome this limitation, a novel autosampler has recently been proposed by Iiterheimova and Kubán [20]. The authors built an open-source autosampler for in-house CE systems, consisting of two parts, an injector unit with sample rack and a rinsing unit with pressure pump (28.5 cm × 20.5 cm × 16 cm). Injection is based on the siphon effect by automatically lifting the entire sample carousel higher than the

outlet. The device was completely controlled by an Arduino Mega microcontroller. The injections were performed from open vials, which limited the application of the device to relatively large sample volumes in order to avoid errors due to the evaporation of water from the containers [20].

This report describes the development of a new compact single module autosampler (9 cm width, 9 cm depth, 26 cm height). To the best of our knowledge, this is the first example of an in-house made compact autosampler using hydrodynamic injection by pressure. The system presents a fully automated sample injection system, that reduces the operator intervention, significantly limiting the potential sources of error compared to traditional manual injection methods. Also, the device was designed using an open-source hardware approach, enabling easy upgrades, seamless integration of new features, and the development of complementary instruments, making the system highly flexible to novel challenges and evolving requirements.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

All chemicals were of analytical grade. Potassium chloride was obtained from Merck (Zug, Switzerland). Sodium chloride, sodium hydroxide, magnesium chloride, and barium chloride were purchased from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland). Calcium chloride and acetic acid glacial were acquired from VWR (Dietikon, Switzerland). L-Histidine, and 18-crown-6 were bought from Sigma-Aldrich (Buchs, Switzerland). All solutions were prepared using deionised ultrapure water prepared on a MilliQ system from Millipore (Bedford, MA, USA).

2.2. CE-system

The movements of liquids through the CE instrument, including sample injection, washing and conditioning of the capillary, were controlled by a pneumatic system. This was an adaptation from our previously published low cost instrument (albeit without autosampler) [2]. A schematic drawing is shown in Fig. 1. Compressed air from a standard cylinder (PanGas, Pratteln, Switzerland) fitted with a conventional regulator set to an outlet pressure of 6 bar was employed. The pressure was further reduced with the help of two precision regulators to obtain the two levels required for the operation of the liquid manifold, 4 bar for capillary flushing and 0.6 bar for sample injection. The first pressure regulator (DR-2, Clippard, Cincinnati, OH, USA) down-regulates the pressure to 4 bar, the second one (DR-2-5, Clippard) to a lower value between 0.3 and 0.9 bar. The two pressures are applied to the liquid manifold by opening either of the two latching valves LV1 or LV2 (E2L10C-7W012, Clippard). A third latching valve (LV3) allows depressurization. The valves were mounted on single station manifolds (E10M01, Clippard). LV1 and LV2 were fitted at the outlets with check-valves (MCV-1O2, Clippard) and LV3 with a muffler (15070, Clippard). The pressures were set with the help of two pressure gauges with ranges of 0–25 bar (Swagelok, Solon, OH, USA) and 0–2.5 bar (HLüdi, Regensdorf, Switzerland). The gas lines were implemented with 1/8" O.D. tubing (Clippard) and a cross connector (UTF-2002, Clippard) and three T-connectors (UT0-2002, Clippard). A pressure sensor (PSE532-M5, SMC, Weisslingen, Switzerland) connected via a connector (UT0-F0F-PKG, Clippard) to the gas line of the autosampler, was used for measuring the time required for reaching the set value of pressure. The measurements have been performed with the help of an

oscilloscope (Picoscope 4262, Pico Technology, St Neots, UK).

The high voltage for the electrophoretic separation was applied at the detector end of the capillary (365 μm O.D., 25 μm I.D.; TSP-025375, Molex-Polymicro, Phoenix, AZ, USA). This was inserted into a liquid reservoir (BBRES-1ML-T116 for 1/16" tubing) from LabSmith (Livermore, CA, USA). The separation voltage was provided by a high voltage module (UM30N4/S, Spellman, Pulborough, UK) using a high voltage wire inserted into a second liquid reservoir which was connected to the first one by means of a PTFE tube 1/16" O.D. 0.50 mm I.D. x 2.5 cm (BGB, Boeckten, Switzerland). The high voltage section was isolated by means of a polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) case equipped with a safety microswitch that interrupts the high voltage on opening its cover. Signals were measured with a contactless conductivity detector previously reported [21], which was connected to a C⁴D data acquisition system (e-corder 410, eDAQ, Denistone East, NSW, Australia), and the associated software (PowerChrom; eDAQ).

The system was controlled with a MSP430FR2433 Launchpad (Texas Instruments, Dallas, TX, USA) which was connected to a purpose-made printed circuit board (PCB) providing the necessary electronic interfaces to the CE-system as well as the autosampler. See the block diagram of Fig. 2. The voltage of the high-voltage power supply was set with help of a digital-to-analog converter (DAC, MAX517, purchased from Digikey Corporation, Thief River Falls, MN, US). A voltage-level translator (PCA9306; Texas Instruments, Dallas, TX, US) allowed the communication between the DAC and the MSP430FR2433 Launchpad. The H-bridge drivers (BD6220F-E2; Rohm, Kyoto, Japan) manage reversal of the voltage for activating/de-activating the latching valves. The Launchpad was programmed with the open source Mecrisp Forth language (<https://mecrisp.sourceforge.net/>). Interaction with the user was achieved via the serial terminal emulator CoolTerm (<http://freeware.the-meiers.org/>) running on a PC connected to the Launchpad via USB. Details on this approach can be found in a previous publication [22].

2.3. Autosampler

The needle (G1600-60007, Electrode Assembly) and the pre-puncher (G1600-60007, Electrode Assembly) were obtained from Agilent (Santa Clara, CA, US). These are spare parts for their bench-top CE instruments (G1600 and CE7100). The inlet of the separation capillary was fixed to this assembly using a tubing sleeve (Nanotight 1/16" FEP; BGB, Boeckten, Switzerland). The two stepper motors were a hybrid stepper motor (Nema 17, MOT-ST-42-L-A-A, Iigus, Cologne, Germany) and

unipolar stepper motor (28BYJ-48 ULN2003, Amazon, Seattle, WA, USA). The former was controlled via an A4988 stepper motor driver (Purecrea; Digitec Galaxus AG, Zurich, Switzerland) mounted on an A4988 control board (Purecrea) which in turn was connected to the controller PCB (see Fig. 2). The motor was fitted with a lead screw (1.5 mm x 85 mm x 8 mm - pitch x length x diameter) and a lead screw nut (iglidur® J JFRM-202020TR8X1.5). The unipolar stepper motor (28BYJ-48) was controlled using the integrated circuit driver ULN2003 connected to the PCB, which was provided with the stepper motor by the seller (Amazon). The sample carousel was also made from PMMA, and was designed to hold six vials (5182-0567 Polypropylene Vial, 1 mL; Agilent). The details of each part are included in the supplementary materials.

2.4. Electrophoretic conditions and sample preparation

The device was tested using an already published method for detecting cations [2]. Briefly, all separations were performed in a fused silica capillary (25 μm I.D., 42.5 cm effective length, 55 cm total length) by applying a voltage of 20 kV and using a background electrolyte (BGE) consisting of 15 mM l-histidine, 50 mM acetic acid and 5 mM 18-crown-6. New silica capillaries were washed with NaOH 0.1 mol/L (30 min) and then with deionised water for 30 min. Each day the capillary was rinsed with a solution containing NaOH 0.1 mol/L (10 min), followed by deionised water (10 min) and finally conditioned with the BGE (10 min) or until the baseline was stable, if required. Before each sequence of analyses, the capillary was rinsed as previously described, reducing the time for each step to 5 min. This process was repeated between each sequence of analyses, allowing five samples to be analysed in succession. Between each run the capillary was rinsed for 1 min with the background electrolyte. Three brands of mineral water were purchased from a local supermarket (Coop, Basel, Switzerland). The samples were diluted ten, twenty and forty times in the BGE before analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Design of the autosampler

The autosampler proposed in this study features a rotary six-position vial tray. The vials contain samples, BGE or flushing solutions. Rotation is achieved with a stepper motor. Flushing and sample injection is carried out by lowering a hollow needle containing the capillary into a vial

Fig. 1. Instrument. Diagram of the electropneumatic part. C⁴D: capacitively coupled contactless conductivity detector.

Fig. 2. Electronic circuitry. Scheme of the device components managed with the MSP430FR2433 Launchpad. I2C: inter-integrated circuit, a serial communication bus; DAC: digital-to-analog convertor; TTL: transistor transistor logic, on/off-control signals.

with a second stepper motor. The vials are sealed to allow pressurization of the headspace for displacement of the liquid into the capillary. The seal also avoids evaporation of the solvent from samples and associated measurement errors. Two pressures are available, 4 bar for flushing of the capillary, and a lower pressure (typically 0.6 bar) for precisely controlled injection of samples. A 50 L (200 bar) air cylinder was used for the study, providing an almost inexhaustible supply of air. However, with a view to using the unit for portable instruments, the estimated number of analyses using a 0.3 L (8 bar) air cylinder was almost 190,

making the system adequate for on-site analysis. The operations are controlled and sequenced by software running on a microcontroller (MSP430FR2433). The user initiates the sampler operations from the PC used for the measurements with the help of a serial terminal program.

In the development of the autosampler it was aimed to minimize the overall size of the device while still having the ability to automate the injection of multiple samples. A schematic drawing of the device and a photograph are shown in Fig. 3. The assembly was based on PMMA and has three moving parts: sample carousel, a pre-puncher module and a

Fig. 3. Autosampler. a) Diagram of the autosampler (the details of each are included in the supplementary materials); b) image of the autosampler.

needle module. The carousel is mounted directly on one of the two stepper motors and a 60-degree rotation achieves the movement between two vials. The placement of the capillary into a sample/buffer container is achieved by a linear movement from the stand-by (up) to the injection (down) position (Fig. 3 shows the stand-by position). The movement between the two positions was actuated by a second stepper motor which was fitted with a lead screw, resulting in a vertical displacement of 1.5 mm for one full rotation of the motor. However, in order to allow the insertion of the needle into a vial, its cap must be perforated. The rotation of the lead screw therefore also moves a pre-puncher module. The pre-puncher penetrates the vial cap with a hollow guide for inserting the needle with the capillary. It also provides a path for pressurization of the headspace of the vial during the injection of the sample or flushing of the capillary. The needle and pre-puncher modules move simultaneously as can be seen in the multimedia file in the supplementary materials. The entire process was fully automated and managed via the software used to run the sample analysis. The actuation of the stepper motor moves the pre-puncher in a time-controlled manner, both in terms of displacement speed and position. On this basis, the perforation of the cap and the injection of the needle with capillary were effective and reproducible. Note, that the hollow needle containing the capillary also serves as the electrophoretic ground electrode.

The motors for actuating the movements were selected on the basis of size, cost, commercial availability, and function. Stepper motors were employed because they allow precise control of their position without the need of a position sensor for feedback. However, the stepper motor used for lowering the pre-puncher also has to have a relatively high torque (0.5 Nm) in order to guarantee that no leakage of air occurs during pressurization of the vials for capillary rinsing and hydrodynamic sample injection.

3.2. Study of the injection parameters

In order to evaluate the autosampler, a solution composed of three cations, *i.e.*, sodium, calcium and magnesium, was used as a model sample. The separation conditions were based on a previously developed method [2]. The injection parameters time and pressure were optimized by carrying out a series of injection at pressures of 0.3, 0.6 and 0.9 bar and evaluating the signal-to-noise ratio and resolution. The results for sodium and the sodium/calcium pair, respectively, are given in Fig. 4. Similar results were obtained for the other peaks, and are given in the supplementary material. As expected, an increase of the injection time generally led to an improved signal-to-noise ratio, but a diminished resolution, so that a compromise has to be made. Note, that in principle for equal products of pressure and injection time identical results should be obtained. However, a comparison of the results obtained for the different pressures shows that this is not the case.

This was found to be due to delays in building up the pressure on opening the pneumatic valve. These were determined to be 2'176 ms (± 144), 73 ms (± 7), and 63 ms (± 1) for 0.3, 0.6 and 0.9 bar respectively (to reach 90 % of the final values). This delay was therefore significant for the injections at 0.3 bar but deemed negligible for the higher pressures. All subsequent experiments were carried out using a pressure of 0.6 bar and an injection time of 3'590 ms as compromise conditions for signal-to-noise ratio and resolution. This, incidentally, corresponds closely to the recommendation of using sample plugs of a length of 2 % of the effective length of capillary, as described by Carrilho et al. [9].

3.3. Performance

3.3.1. Precision of injection

The injection performance was evaluated by determining the repeatability of the signal by injecting from the same vial and from different vials. Intra-vial repeatability was verified by injecting fifteen times from the same vial and calculating the relative standard deviation

Fig. 4. Signal-to-noise and resolution. Overlapping of the sodium signal-to-noise ratio (empty symbol) and the resolution between sodium and calcium (filled symbol) as function of the injection time (x-axis). The variation was investigated at three values of pressure of injection: a) 0.3 bar (circle); b) 0.6 bar (square); c) 0.9 bar (triangle), using a solution 100 μ M of sodium, calcium and magnesium. For the separation condition refer to section 2.4.

(RSD%) of migration time, peak area and resolution between the three peaks. The RSD% of migration times, peak areas and resolutions were less than 0.50 %, 2.40 % and 2.90 % respectively (Table 1). The inter-vial repeatability was verified by random single injection from five different positions of the sample carousel and the same parameters were calculated from the results. The RSD% of migration times, peak areas and resolutions were less than 0.40 %, 2.10 % and 2.70 %, respectively (Table 2). All measurements were performed without internal standard.

3.3.2. Carry-over, peak efficiency and detection limits

Due to the immersion of the needle in different solutions during a series of analyses there is a potential carry over. This was therefore assessed by performing a series of three analyses (a solution 100 μM of calcium, sodium, and magnesium) with an intermediate analysis of the BGE solution without analyte present. As shown in Fig. 5, no discernible peaks were present in the electropherograms for the BGE solutions.

On the basis of the obtained electropherograms (Fig. 5), the peak efficiency expressed as plate number was 1.3×10^4 , which was comparable with the results obtained in the same separative conditions in another report [2].

The detection limits for the five ions ammonium, potassium, calcium, sodium and magnesium were then determined in terms of both, limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ). The LOD and LOQ were estimated for three replicates for each level as three and ten times the signal-to-noise ratio, respectively. The LODs for the analytes were within 5 and 11 μM and the LOQs ranged from 20 to 37 μM . These values are close to previously obtained results using a similar CE- C^4D system without autosampler [17]. LODs, LOQs and linearity data are shown in Table 3.

3.3.3. Analysis of mineral waters

Prior to each series of analyses, the capillary was rinsed with NaOH 0.1 M, water and BGE for 5 min each. The rinsing was repeated every five runs so that a sequence of five samples could be run without operator intervention. After rinsing the capillary, the calibration curve was plotted using five solutions at different concentration levels. Following the calibration curve sequence, three different commercial mineral water samples were analysed, and the results are presented in Table 4. In agreement with the concentrations reported on the label, calcium was found to be the most abundant cation with concentrations of 89, 448 and 154 mg/L for samples 1, 2 and 3 respectively. On the other hand, the less abundant ion was potassium with values below 2.5 mg/L. Magnesium was found within the range from 25.7 to 55.8 mg/L, while sodium concentrations were 6.1, 6.0 and 12.4 mg/L for samples 1, 2 and 3, respectively. The accuracies of determination (with reference to the specification on the labels) were within 94 and 112 %, except for sodium in samples 2 and 3, which were 127 and 129 %, respectively, and the

Table 1

Method validation: Intra-vial repeatability. The intra-vial repeatability was determined by injecting fifteen times from the same vial. The precision of analysis was determined in terms of relative standard deviation for migration times, peak areas, and resolution.

	t_m , min	RSD% (n = 15)
Ca^{2+}	3.41	0.48
Na^+	3.56	0.49
Mg^{2+}	3.70	0.47
	Area, mV·s	RSD% (n=15)
Ca^{2+}	212.6	2.18
Na^+	124.4	2.37
Mg^{2+}	209.6	1.66
	Resolution	RSD% (n=15)
$\text{Na}^+ - \text{Ca}^{2+}$	1.93	2.81
$\text{Mg}^{2+} - \text{Na}^+$	1.85	2.61

Table 2

Method validation: Inter-vial repeatability. The inter-vial repeatability was determined by randomly injecting from five different positions of the samples carousel. The precision of analysis was determined in terms of relative standard deviation for migration times, peak areas, and resolutions.

	t_m , min	RSD% (n = 5)
Ca^{2+}	3.29	0.39
Na^+	3.42	0.38
Mg^{2+}	3.56	0.46
	Area, mV·s	RSD% (n=5)
Ca^{2+}	195.1	1.65
Na^+	115.1	2.10
Mg^{2+}	193.2	1.60
	Resolution	RSD% (n=5)
$\text{Na}^+ - \text{Ca}^{2+}$	1.77	1.76
$\text{Mg}^{2+} - \text{Na}^+$	2.07	2.69

Fig. 5. Carry-over. Sequence of three analysis of a solution 100 μM of calcium, sodium, and magnesium. After the analysis of the solution containing the three ions, a running buffer solution has been analysed for verifying the presence of detectable signals. For the separation condition refer to section 2.4.

Table 3

Method validation: sensitivity and linearity. LOD, LOQ, and linearity parameters for each analyte.

	LOD, μM	LOQ, μM	Calibration equation	Correlation coefficient, R^2
Ammonium	6.6	22.1	$y = 1.372(\pm 0.061) x - 0.011(\pm 0.001)$	0.9999
Potassium	8.4	27.8	$y = 1.215(\pm 0.044) x - 0.006(\pm 0.001)$	0.9999
Calcium	6.1	20.4	$y = 1.916(\pm 0.052) x - 0.012(\pm 0.002)$	0.9999
Sodium	11	36.7	$y = 1.150(\pm 0.049) x - 0.012(\pm 0.002)$	0.9995
Magnesium	5.0	16.7	$y = 1.889(\pm 0.028) x - 0.004(\pm 0.002)$	0.9999

accuracy of determination for the potassium of sample 3, which was 72.0 % (Table 4).

4. Conclusions

An autosampler employing hydrodynamic injection by pressure to

Table 4

Analysis of drinking water samples. The concentration reported is the average of four determinations, and the uncertainty of the measurement is reported as standard deviation.

	Cations	Concentration found, mg/L	Concentration declared, mg/L	Accuracy
Sample 1	Potassium	1.1 (± 0.2)	1.0	110.2
	Calcium	88.7 (± 5.1)	80.0	110.8
	Sodium	6.1 (± 2.3)	6.5	93.5
	Magnesium	29.1 (± 2.9)	26.0	111.8
Sample 2	Potassium	–	–	–
	Calcium	448.1 (± 25.6)	435.0	103.0
	Sodium	11.9 (± 1.5)	9.4	126.9
	Magnesium	58.1 (± 5.0)	55.0	105.6
Sample 3	Potassium	2.4 (± 0.1)	3.4	72.0
	Calcium	153.5 (± 7.9)	145.0	105.8
	Sodium	6.0 (± 2.2)	4.6	129.4
	Magnesium	25.7 (± 2.1)	23.8	108.0

minimize manual operations in capillary electrophoresis has been described. The device was built entirely in-house, following the idea of Open-Source Hardware (OSH), and all information regarding the construction of the autosampler is provided in the supporting material of the present report. The multi-injection system has been successfully combined with an also in-house made capillary electrophoresis instrument. The performance of the assembly was tested and its injection reproducibility of better than 2.4 % was found to be comparable with commercial CE instruments. However, the presented device is more affordable considering that the cost is approximately €1100 (detailed information is provided in the supplementary materials) and, as previously demonstrated, the cost of other CE parts is approximately €6500 [2]. The small dimensions of the autosampler (9 cm width, 9 cm depth, 26 cm height) potentially allow its integration into a portable instrument. It features six vial positions, but this could be increased if the overall size is not critical.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Giacomo Musile: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Marc-Aurèle Boillat:** Investigation. **Peter C. Hauser:** Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2025.343835>.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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